

Preliminary study on the effects of stochastic variations in the geometric and mechanical properties of bamboo culms on the compression capacity of round bamboo columns

Ryuga KARAHASHI*, Takuo NAGAI^a, Eisuke MITSUDA^b

* Architecture (Master's Program), Kyoto Institute of Technology
1 Hashikami-cho, Matsugasaki, Sakyou-ku, Kyoto-city, Kyoto, Japan
to13kawahashi@ec.usp.ac.jp

^a The University of Shiga Prefecture, Shiga, Japan

^b Faculty of Design and Architecture, Kyoto Institute of Technology, Kyoto, Japan

Abstract

This study investigates the reliability of the compression strength of round bamboo columns based on Ylinen's formula. The Monte Carlo method is employed to evaluate the effects of probabilistic variations in culm diameter, wall thickness, flattening ratio, Young's modulus, and crushing strength on compression strength. The results show that variations in mechanical properties, particularly Young's modulus and crushing strength, have a more significant impact than geometric variations. Additionally, compression strength does not always increase with culm diameter; instead, there exists an optimal culm diameter that maximizes strength for a given effective buckling length. Beyond this diameter, both strength and structural reliability decrease due to increased variability. The study also examines the influence of cross-sectional modeling and finds that while different modeling approaches result in slight deviations, the selection of a specific cross-section does not critically impact strength evaluation. The findings emphasize the importance of selecting an appropriate culm diameter and ensuring a sufficient safety margin against buckling in bamboo column design.

Keywords: bamboo structures, round bamboo, full-culm bamboo, structural reliability, compression strength, stochastic variations, Ylinen's formula.

1. Introduction

Bamboo, in addition to its excellent mechanical properties, possesses a short harvesting cycle, strong regenerative capacity, and remarkable carbon sequestration ability, making it a material with significant potential as a sustainable building material. As the world moves towards the realization of a carbon-neutral society, bamboo is increasingly anticipated as one of the viable options for construction materials, and international momentum for research and development is growing. However, there remain numerous challenges in utilizing bamboo as a structural material. In the case of "round bamboo (full-culm bamboo) structures," which use bamboo in its natural form, the publication of ISO 22156:2021 [1] has provided a framework for structural design, albeit with limitations to two-story structures or fewer. Nevertheless, applying bamboo's excellent mechanical properties and light weight to larger-span spatial structures presents a highly beneficial and intriguing challenge.

It is well known that in spatial structures, the evaluation of joint eccentricity and stiffness has a significant influence on buckling strength (IASS WG8 [2]), and there are concerns that irregularities in the shape of bamboo members and joints may exacerbate these effects in round bamboo structures composed of bamboo culms with natural form.

Therefore, this study focuses on individual bamboo columns, investigating methods for modeling round bamboo structures and evaluating the effects of stochastic variations in the geometric and mechanical properties of bamboo on structural responses, with a particular focus on the impact of these variations on buckling strength through numerical analysis.

2. Method of stochastic analysis

2.1. Target structure and parameters

The model considered in this study is a simple column (two-dimensional model) composed of a single round bamboo culm (full-culm bamboo), and the probabilistic variation in its compression strength is examined. The bamboo materials used in this study are Japanese Madake (*Phyllostachys bambusoides*) and Moso bamboo (*Phyllostachys edulis*). Fig. 1 illustrates the factors influencing the compression strength of round bamboo columns. The parameters affecting the compression strength of round bamboo columns are classified into mechanical properties and geometric properties. The mechanical properties considered are the Young's modulus E and crushing strength f_c , while the geometric properties include the culm diameter D , culm wall thickness t , and cross-sectional oval ratio ζ . The variation analysis is conducted using the Monte Carlo method, following the procedure below. Based on the experimental results of Nagai et al. [3, 4], the statistical characteristics and correlations of these parameters are organized, and a regression model is developed. Using this regression model, random number generation is applied to simulate the parameters, and sample values of compression strength are computed. By repeating this process, the probabilistic variation in compression strength is evaluated.

Furthermore, the influence of cross-sectional variation along the longitudinal direction (tapering characteristics) on compression strength is analyzed separately in Section 4. Note that this study focuses on straight bamboo culms, and the effect of initial out-of-straightness (geometric imperfection) is left for future investigation.

Figure 1. Factors affecting the compression strength of round bamboo columns.

2.2. Formulation of the regression model for mechanical properties

When utilizing round bamboo culms as structural members, the most easily measurable characteristic through visual inspection and non-destructive methods is the culm diameter. Therefore, it is most reasonable to formulate each mechanical property as a function of the culm diameter D . Fig. 2 presents the relationship between culm diameter and each parameter (Nagai et al. [3, 4]), as well as the distribution of the oval ratio ζ for Japanese Madake and Moso bamboo. As shown in the figure, the four parameters exhibit a linear correlation with D . The red solid line represents the regression line obtained by the least squares method, while the pink solid lines indicate the 95% confidence interval. When determining the confidence interval, no significant difference in the standard deviation was observed due to variations in culm diameter, and thus it was assumed to be a constant value. Additionally, Table 1 summarizes the regression equations, as well as the mean and standard deviation of each characteristic value across the entire sample.

The cross-section of a round bamboo culm in its natural form is not a perfect circle. However, it is generally modeled as a perfect circle in structural analysis. In this study, the cross-section of round

bamboo is represented as an ellipse, and the deviation between the maximum and minimum diameter from a perfect circle is expressed using the oval ratio ζ , defined as follows:

$$\zeta = \frac{D_{\max} - D_{\min}}{D_{av}}, \quad D_{av} = \frac{S}{\pi} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. The distribution of the oval ratio and relationship between culm diameter and various parameters.

Table 1. Statistical values and regression equations of each parameter.

Species	ζ		t [mm]		E [MPa]		f_c [MPa]	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Madake	0.000	0.049	5.00	0.88	12515	2501	75.5	12.5
	-	-	$t = 0.0629D + 0.44$		$E = -183.17D + 25520$		$f_c = -0.2645D + 94.6$	
Moso bamboo	0.000	0.052	6.30	0.71	11284	1933	68.1	11.0
	-	-	$t = 0.0714D + 1.21$		$E = -159.52D + 22103$		$f_c = -0.3312D + 91.7$	

S.D.: Standard deviation at each diameter (constant), ζ : oval ratio, t: culm wall thickness, E: Young's modulus, f_c : crushing strength

Figure 3. Initial out-of-straightness of bamboo culms.

Here, D_{\max} represents the maximum diameter of the cross-section, D_{\min} represents the minimum diameter, and S denotes the outer perimeter of the bamboo culm. Fig. 2(a) illustrates the oval ratio ζ of bamboo culm cross-sections. It can be observed that for both bamboo species, ζ can be approximately modeled by a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of approximately 0.05 (5%). Additionally, Fig. 3 presents the results of an investigation into the initial out-of-straightness of

randomly selected bamboo culms, each approximately 2 m in length, including 20 specimens of Madake and 12 specimens of Moso bamboo. The horizontal axis represents the normalized coordinate along the culm axis (coordinate x divided by total length L). The vertical axis represents the normalized initial out-of-straightness in the NS (y) and EW (z) directions, measured as the deviation from the straight line connecting the centroid of the cross-sections at both ends of the member, divided by the L . The initial out-of-straightness tends to be slightly larger in Moso bamboo than Madake, with its maximum deviation reaching approximately 1/50 of the total length.

2.3. Compression strength of round bamboo columns based on Ylinen's formula

In this study, the design compression capacity P_{cr} is determined using Ylinen's formula (Ylinen [5], Zahn [6]), which is adopted in ISO 22156, as follows:

$$P_{cr} = \frac{P_c + P_e}{2c} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{P_c + P_e}{2c}\right)^2 - \frac{P_c \cdot P_e}{c}} \quad (2)$$

where P_c represents the crushing capacity and P_e represents the elastic buckling capacity, which are obtained using the following equations:

$$P_c = f_c \sum A \quad (3)$$

$$P_e = \frac{n\pi^2 E_d I_{\min} C_{bow}}{(KL)^2} \quad \text{or} \quad P_e = \frac{n\pi^2 (EI)_{d,\min} C_{bow}}{(KL)^2} \quad (4)$$

where, f_c : allowable crushing stress, E_d : design Young's modulus, n : number of members composing the column, I_{\min} : minimum second moment of area among the bamboo culm cross-sections forming the column, $(EI)_{d,\min}$: minimum bending stiffness among the bamboo culms composing the column, KL : effective buckling length. The design Young's modulus E_d is determined from experimental results, using $E_{0.50}$ (the 50% lower bound at a 75% confidence level). The allowable crushing strength f_c is obtained by multiplying $f_{c,0.05}$ (the 5% lower bound at a 75% confidence level) by various adjustment factors, which are set to 1 in this study. Since this study focuses on a column composed of a single round bamboo culm, $n = 1$, and the bending stiffness is represented by $E_d I_{\min}$. C_{bow} is a knockdown factor that reduces the elastic buckling strength according to the magnitude of the initial out-of-straightness value b_{max} of the bamboo culm, and is expressed by the following equation:

$$C_{bow} = 1 - \frac{b_0}{0.02}, \quad b_0 = \frac{b_{max}}{L} \quad (5)$$

As shown in Fig. 3, the normalized initial out-of-straightness b_0 reaches a maximum value of approximately 0.04, while the mean values are 0.004 for Madake and 0.006 for Moso bamboo. This indicates that C_{bow} has a significant influence on the design compression strength. However, for simple columns, the reduction caused by C_{bow} results in a substantial deviation from the actual strength. Therefore, in this study, only straight members ($C_{bow} = 1$) are considered, and the linear buckling load (Euler buckling load) is used for P_e .

The compression strength is defined as $f_{cr} = P_{cr}/A$. Fig. 4 illustrates the relationship between the slenderness ratio λ and compression strength f_{cr} . The black solid line represents the results using mean experimental values from Table 1 for reference. The colored solid lines represent results obtained using the regression equations for culm diameter and various parameters, as given in the same table. The analysis considers four effective buckling lengths ($KL = 500, 1000, 2000, 3000$ mm) and culm diameters ranging from 40 to 120 mm. When considering the correlation between culm diameter and material properties, the compression strength does not reach its maximum at $\lambda = 0$ but instead attains a peak at a certain slenderness ratio. This occurs because as the culm diameter increases and the

slenderness ratio decreases, both Young’s modulus and crushing strength tend to decrease. Therefore, in round bamboo columns, there exists an “optimal culm diameter” that maximizes the compression strength for a given effective buckling length. Table 2 summarizes the optimal diameters at each effective buckling length. It is important to note that a larger cross-section does not necessarily lead to higher compression strength.

Figure 4. Relationship between slenderness ratio and compression strength in round bamboo columns.

Table 2. Optimal culm diameter and slenderness ratio at each effective buckling length.

Species		L = 500 mm	L = 1,000 mm	L = 2,000 mm	L = 3,000 mm
Madake	D _{opt}	64.0	82.7	90.7	93.3
	λ _{opt}	24.1	37.2	67.8	98.9
Moso bamboo	D _{opt}	53.3	82.7	93.3	93.3
	λ _{opt}	29.1	37.3	65.9	98.9

D_{opt}: optimal culm diameter, λ_{opt}: slenderness ratio at D_{opt}

2.4. Monte Carlo simulation method

As discussed earlier, since the Young’s modulus and crushing strength of bamboo vary with culm diameter D , the compression strength cannot be uniquely determined for the same slenderness ratio. Therefore, to account for practical applications such as small-scale buildings (one to two stories) or members of truss structures, appropriate member lengths ($KL = 500, 1,000, 2,000, 3,000$ mm) are considered, and compression strength calculations are performed using culm diameter as a parameter.

Culm diameter is the most easily measurable parameter for designers using non-destructive methods. However, the diameter of bamboo varies depending on the position along the culm. ISO 22156 prescribes the use of the minimum cross-sectional dimension for structural members, but to achieve a more accurate evaluation of structural behavior, it is considered more appropriate to use the mean diameter over the entire length of the member. Therefore, in this study, the culm diameter D is assumed to remain constant along the whole member length, and various characteristic values are calculated based on this assumption. For a given characteristic value f , its variation is assumed to follow a normal distribution centered around its mean and is expressed as a function of D as follows:

$$f(D) = \mu_f(D) + \varepsilon_f, \quad \varepsilon_f = N(0, \sigma_f) \quad (6)$$

where, $\mu_f(D)$: mean value of $f(D)$, σ_f : Standard deviation of f , $\varepsilon_f = N(0, \sigma_f)$: normally distributed random variable with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of σ_f . The mean values of each characteristic are obtained using the regression equations provided in Table 1.

Additionally, based on the oval ratio ζ , the major diameter D_{\max} and minor diameter D_{\min} of the bamboo culm are determined using the following equations. These values are then used to calculate the cross-sectional area and the second moment of area in the weak axis direction:

$$D_{\max} = \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{2}\right)D, \quad D_{\min} = \left(1 - \frac{\zeta}{2}\right)D \quad (7)$$

The culm diameter considered in the analysis ranges from 40 mm to 120 mm. The diameter is varied in 1 mm increments, and for each culm diameter, 30 random samples are generated to compute the compression strength. Using these 30 results per culm diameter, the statistical values of compression strength are then calculated for each culm diameter D .

3. Results of analysis

3.1. Influence of each characteristic value on design compression strength

Fig. 5 illustrates the coefficient of variation (COV) of compression strength f_{cr} when only one characteristic value is varied probabilistically, while keeping all other parameters constant at their mean values. As previously mentioned, correlations exist among characteristic values, making this variation assumption unrealistic. However, this analysis helps to individually assess the influence of each characteristic on the compression strength formula and its fundamental properties.

Figure 5. Coefficient of variation (COV) of compression strength when each parameter is varied independently.

For geometric properties, in both bamboo species, the influence of culm wall thickness t is greater than that of the oval ratio ζ . Therefore, approximating the bamboo culm cross-section as a nearly perfect circle is reasonable. As the slenderness ratio increases, elastic buckling strength becomes dominant, amplifying the effect of variations in t . For mechanical properties, in the low-slenderness region, variations in crushing strength f_c have a significant impact. However, for members with slenderness ratios corresponding to $L = 2,000$ mm or more, variations in f_c have almost no effect on compression strength. On the other hand, for the Young's modulus E , its influence on the variation of compression strength increases as member length increases. In particular, for all member lengths, as the culm diameter increases, the relative variation in Young's modulus compared to its mean value also increases, leading to a rapid increase in the variability of compression strength. This trend is uncommon in other structural materials.

Fig. 6 shows the coefficient of variation of compression strength f_{cr} when all four parameters are varied simultaneously. As demonstrated in the previous analysis of Young's modulus, as the slenderness ratio decreases, the coefficient of variation increases rapidly. Additionally, for both bamboo species, when the culm diameter falls below the optimal culm diameter, the rate of change in the coefficient of variation slows down, eventually stabilizing at approximately 0.15.

Figure 6. Coefficient of variation (COV) of compression strength considering variations in all parameters.

3.2. Comparison of statistical compression strength and iso formula

Fig. 7 illustrates the ratio of $f_{cr, monte, 0.05}$, the 5% lower bound of compression strength at a 75% confidence level, obtained through Monte Carlo simulation, to $f_{cr, ISO}$, the compression strength derived from the ISO formula Eq. (2). For $L = 500$ mm, where the influence of the elastic buckling load P_e is minimal, this ratio ranges from approximately 0.75 to 1.0. The dots in the figure correspond to the slenderness ratios associated with the optimal culm diameters determined in Table 2. For both bamboo species, the ratio $f_{cr, monte, 0.05}/f_{cr, ISO}$ declines sharply when the culm diameter exceeds the optimal diameter, and converges to an approximately constant value of 0.75 when the diameter is below the optimal value. This indicates that when the culm diameter exceeds the optimal diameter, not only does the compression strength decrease, but its variability also increases significantly. Therefore, in the design of round bamboo columns, it is crucial to accurately evaluate the optimal culm diameter and to select a culm diameter smaller than or equal to the optimal diameter.

Figure 7. Ratio of the 5% lower bound compression strength obtained by Monte Carlo simulation to the ISO compression strength formula $f_{cr, monte, 0.05}/f_{cr, ISO}$.

4. Variation in cross-sectional modeling along the culm axis

Round bamboo culms are variable cross-section members, with continuous changes in their cross-sectional dimensions along their length. Consequently, in structural design, how the cross-section is defined can significantly affect the accuracy of strength and stiffness estimations, making modeling approaches a key design challenge. ISO 22156 prescribes the use of the minimum cross-sectional dimension at the culm ends to ensure a conservative design. However, for structural members approximately 3m in length, the difference in cross-sectional size between both ends can be substantial, making the adoption of the smallest dimension highly inefficient. Furthermore, as previously discussed, the mechanical properties of bamboo exhibit a negative correlation with cross-sectional size, meaning that simply using the smallest cross-section does not necessarily result in a safer strength estimation. To investigate this, we examine the effect of different modeling approaches when replacing bamboo culms with beam elements on design compression strength.

Fig. 8 illustrates the different modeling methods for bamboo culm members, (a) ISO method: the member is modeled as a uniform cross-section with the smallest culm diameter and wall thickness among both ends, (b) average cross-section method: the member is modeled as a uniform cross-section

with the average diameter and wall thickness of both ends, (c) maximum cross-section method: this method opposes (a) by using the largest culm diameter and wall thickness, and (d) refined FEM model: based on the study on morphology of bamboo culm by Nagai [3], this method considers the continuous variation of cross-section along the culm length, the bamboo culm is modeled as an FEM member, and linear buckling analysis is performed to determine the buckling load. In the last method, the culm is divided into 10 segments, with stepwise changes in cross-section to closely simulate the actual bamboo culm shape. Since model (d) most accurately represents the actual bamboo culm form, it is regarded as the “refined model”, serving as the baseline for comparison with models (a)–(c). In all models, the Young’s modulus E is calculated based on the average diameter using the regression equation in Table 1 and is assumed to remain uniform throughout the member length.

Figure 8. Modeling methods of beam members for round bamboo columns.

Fig. 9 presents the relationship between slenderness ratio and the ratio of compression capacity $P_{cr,(a,b,c)}/P_{cr,(d)}$, where: $P_{cr,(a,b,c)}$ represents the compression capacity obtained from models (a)–(c). $P_{cr,(d)}$ represents the refined model capacity. For both bamboo species, the results show that: model (b) closely matches the refined model across all slenderness ratios, with a ratio close to 1. Models (a) and (c) exhibit increasing deviation from the refined model as the slenderness ratio increases. The greatest deviation occurs at $L = 3,000$ mm in the high-slenderness region, but even in this case, the compression capacity ratio remains within approximately $\pm 5\%$ of the refined model’s value.

Thus, for the round bamboo columns examined in this study, the choice of cross-section location in modeling does not introduce significant discrepancies in evaluating compression capacity. Instead, it is more critical to evaluate variations in mechanical properties rather than focusing solely on cross-sectional modeling.

Figure 9. Ratio of compression capacity obtained from uniform cross-section models to the refined model.

5. Conclusion

This study conducted numerical analyses to evaluate the reliability of the compression strength of column members in round bamboo structures by examining the impact of probabilistic variations in geometric and mechanical properties. The effects of geometric variations in bamboo culm morphology—such as cross-sectional oval ratio, culm wall thickness, and tapering characteristics—on compression strength variation were found to be relatively small. In contrast, variations in crushing strength and Young’s modulus had a significantly greater impact on compression strength fluctuations.

Furthermore, the relationship between compression strength and slenderness ratio in bamboo columns exhibits a peak at a specific slenderness ratio, meaning that increasing the culm diameter does not necessarily maximize compression strength. In other words, for each effective buckling length, there exists an “optimal culm diameter” that maximizes compression strength. When the culm diameter exceeds this optimal value, not only does the compression strength decrease, but its probabilistic variability also increases significantly, leading to a considerable loss in structural reliability. Therefore, in the design of round bamboo columns, it is crucial to select a culm diameter smaller than or equal to the optimal culm diameter and ensure a sufficient safety margin against elastic buckling.

Since this study focused on simple columns, variations due to initial out-of-straightness (geometric imperfections) of bamboo culms were not analyzed. However, in more complex structures such as multi-member trusses and space structures, it is essential to examine the effects of initial imperfections and nonlinear buckling loads. Addressing these issues will be a key focus of future research.

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